

Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement of high school students

Honngam Konyak¹; K. Rijingkhum Yimchunger²; Imlikumla Jamir³

¹Assistant Professor, Mokokchung College of Teacher Education, Yimyu, Nagaland, India

²Assistant Professor, Mokokchung College of Teacher Education, Yimyu, Nagaland, India

³Assistant Professor, Mokokchung College of Teacher Education, Yimyu, Nagaland, India

Corresponding Author Email: honngamknyk71@gmail.com

Abstract— Emotional maturity is the ability to understand and manage one's emotions for better adjustment in life. The objective of this study is to examine the emotional maturity of high school students and its impact on their academic achievement. The study population consist of all the high school students enrolled in Mokokchung district' schools, including those in the rural and urban. Using the simple random sampling method, a sample of 200 students from the district was selected for the study. The Emotional Maturity Scale developed by Yashvir Singh and Mahesh Bhargava, in 2008, was employed for gathering information on Emotional Maturity. Data on the academic achievement of high school students was evaluated in the light of their previous class exam results. According to the findings of the current study, no appreciable differences has been found in the high school students' Emotional Maturity according to their type of schools and locality; however, significant difference have been found in their Emotional Maturity based on gender. Academic Achievement and Emotional Maturity significantly correlate among the high school students in Mokokchung district of Nagaland.

Keywords: Academic achievement, Emotional Maturity gender, locality, management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a period of changes in the social, emotional, physical and intellectual aspects of a child leading towards maturity and the proper development of adolescents in all these aspects is essential for their well-being and progress. Adolescents are the future pillars of our society. Their process of transition to maturity is filled with stress and strains; and are prone to issues of engaging in risky behaviour, peer pressure, indiscipline, anger, depression, rivalry and competitions, bullying, shouldering responsibilities of grown-ups, mental and emotional upheavals, need for acceptance and belongingness etc. With technological advancement in this dynamic and complex society, adaptation and adjustments to the changes in their physiological, biological, emotional, cognitive and social set up is not an easy task. Adolescents' ability to self-regulate and manage their emotions and effectively coping with the stress in life has become one of the crucial areas of focus for parents, teachers and the society. If the adolescents are better equipped to face and tackle the challenges of life, it will help them to perform better in their academic, which might further determine their future career and contribution to the society. Therefore, this study was undertaken to study the Emotional Maturity of the adolescents to understand them and to find out whether there is any relationship between their emotional maturity and academic achievement. The findings of the study will help to suggest ways to help the adolescents to take more positive actions in managing their emotions and coping with the stress in life; and for their well-being so that they can become better and productive citizens of our society.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Kumar and Gyanesh (2022) conducted a study on parental involvement and emotional maturity of higher secondary students and revealed positive relationship between them irrespective of the locality of where the students studied in the schools. Chavda and Chaudhary (2021) conducted a study on emotional maturity of higher secondary schools and the findings of the

study revealed no significant differences in the emotional maturity of students with respect to gender and locality. Ganie and Ganai (2021) investigated the emotional maturity and academic achievement among adolescents of Kashmir. The findings of the study revealed majority of the adolescents had moderate level of emotional maturity; boys were found to be more emotionally mature than girls; and private school students were revealed to be academically bright than government school students. The study also found positive correlation between emotional maturity and academic achievement. Jobson (2020) revealed 74% of the adolescents as extremely emotional immature. The study also found no significant difference in the adolescents' emotional maturity with respect to family type, siblings, age and gender. Dave (2019) found emotional maturity to have positive impact on academic achievement of students. Kanaparthi and Rani (2018) found 68% of the adolescents had unstable emotional maturity and girl students were found to have extremely unstable emotional maturity than boys; however, no significant difference was found with respect to locality, type of management and class level. Prathibha and Ashok (2017) found adolescents to be extremely emotionally immature; whereas, males were found to have higher emotional maturity than females; females were found to have higher academic performance than males. Further, no positive relation was found between emotional maturity and academic performance. Review studies by Kumar and Mishra (2016) showed emotional maturity positively impacted the academic achievement of students. Gunasekar and Pugalenti (2015) and Saraswat and Singh (2015) found no significant relationship between emotional maturity and academic achievement of high school students; and no significant difference in emotional maturity with respect to gender and locality. Shafeeq and Thaqib (2015) revealed majority of the secondary students had extremely unstable level of emotional maturity; and emotional maturity had positive impact on the academic achievement of secondary school students.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To ascertain the level Emotional Maturity of high school students.
2. To study the Emotional Maturity of high school students based on gender, locality and management.
3. To study the relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement of high school students.

IV. HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

H01: There is no significant difference in the Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to gender, locality and management.

H02: There is no significance relationship between the emotional maturity and academic achievement of the high school students.

V. DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The study was confined to high school students studying in Grade 9 in the secondary schools of Mokokchung district in the academic year, 2023. The schools taken for the study were affiliated to Nagaland Board of School Education (NBSE), Nagaland only.

VI. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

VI.I. Research Design

The present study adopted the descriptive survey method.

VI.II. Population and Sample

The population consisted of all the high school students enrolled in Grade 9 during the academic year 2023 in the high schools of Mokokchung district, Nagaland. The sample consisted of 200 high school students selected through simple random sampling.

VI.III. Tools and techniques

Emotional Maturity Scale (EMS-SB) by Yashvir Singh and Mahesh Bhargava was employed to collect the data for the study. Marks obtained in the VIII Class of state board were collected for assessing the achievement of high school students. The analysis of the data was done with the help of appropriate statistical technique such as Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

VII. FINDINGS

Objective 1: To ascertain the level of Emotional Maturity of high school students

TABLE 1: Frequency and Percentage distribution of overall Emotional Maturity score of high school students

Sl. No	EMS-SB Raw Score Range	Z-Score Range	Frequency	%	Levels of EMS-SB	Mean
1	185 & above	+2.01 & above	1	0.5	Extremely High	156.30
2	166-184	+1.26 to + 2.00	32	16	High	
3	145-165	+0.51 to +1.25	142	71	Above Average	
4	118-144	-0.50 to +0.50	25	12.5	Average	
Total			200	100		

Table 1 shows the Emotional Maturity scores of high school students. It can be observed that out of 200 respondents, only 1 respondent i.e. 0.5% of the respondents scored in the extremely high range (185 & above); 32 respondents i.e. 16% scored in the high range; majority of the 142 respondents i.e. 71% scored in the above average range (145-165), and 25 respondents (12.5%) scored in the average level (118-144). This implied that the majority of the high school students have above average level of Emotional Maturity.

Objective 2: To study the Emotional Maturity of high school students based on gender, locality and management.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to gender, locality and management.

Table 2: Results of t-test on Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to gender, locality and management

Variables		N	Mean	S.D.	df	t value	S/NS
Gender	Male	94	153.68	10.84	198	3.537	S*
	Female	106	158.61	8.58			
Locality	Rural	84	155.11	10.10	198	1.429	NS*
	Urban	116	157.16	9.87			
Management	Private	80	157.88	10.08	198	1.827	NS*
	Government	120	155.24	9.83			
Total		200					

*At 0.05 level of significance

Table 2 shows the calculated t value (3.537), for the significance of the difference between the means of male and female high students on Emotional Maturity is greater than table value (1.96) for $df=198$ at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the level of Emotional Maturity among male and female high school students cannot be accepted.” Therefore, “there is significant difference between the Emotional Maturity of male and female high school students.”

The calculated t value (1.429), for the significance of the difference between the means of rural and urban high students on Emotional Maturity is less than table value (1.96) for $df=198$ at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of Emotional Maturity between rural and urban high school students cannot be rejected.

Further, the calculated t value (1.827), for the significance of the difference between the means of private and government high students on Emotional Maturity is less than table value (1.96) for $df=198$ at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of Emotional Maturity between private and government high school students is not rejected. Therefore, “there is no significant difference between the Emotional Maturity of private and government high school students.”

Objective 3: To study the relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement of high school students.

H₀: There is no significant difference in the relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement of high school students.

TABLE 3: Correlation between Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement of high school students

Variables	'r' value	S/NS
Emotional Maturity Academic Achievement	0.079	S*

From table 3, the correlation coefficient is 0.079 and the significant value indicates low positive correlation between Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement of high school students at 0.05 level of significant. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. It can be stated that “there is a significant positive correlation between Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement of high school students.”

VIII. DISCUSSION

The present study revealed majority of the high school students to have an above average level of Emotional Maturity. This finding is in contrast to the study by Ganie and Ganai (2021) where majority of the adolescents were found to have moderate level of emotional maturity. This may be due to the positive environmental factors where the adolescents are brought up - spending quality time with peers, families, relatives, neighbours and community; active involvement in different social groups and social institutions from a young age; sense of responsibility towards parents, siblings, peers, elders and community ingrained in them by their families and their community; and active participation in co-curricular activities at home and at school.

The study found no significant difference in the Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to management which is consistent with the findings of management Kanaparthi and Rani, (2018); but is contradictory to the findings of Shafeeq and Thaqib (2015) which found higher emotional maturity among the government secondary school students than the private secondary school students. The study also revealed no significant difference in the Emotional Maturity of the high school students based on locality which is with the findings of Chavda and Chaudhary (2021), Kanaparthi and Rani (2018), and Saraswat and Singh (2015). The study revealed significant difference with respect to gender, where male high school students had higher level of Emotional Maturity with a mean difference of 2.26 than the female school students. This finding is consistent with the study of Ganie and Ganai (2021) and Prathibha and Ashok (2017) where boys were found to be more emotionally mature than girls; but is in contrast to the study where no significant differences was found in the Emotional Maturity of secondary school students with respect to gender (Chavda & Chaudhary, 2021; Jobson, 2020; Gunasekar & Pugalenti, 2015; Saraswat & Singh, 2015; Shafeeq & Thaqib, 2015). The reasons may be due to the patriarchal set up of the society which influences the parenting style where boys are assigned more responsibilities outside the home and thus have more exposure to outside life and people which may have enabled them to be more outspoken and deal with different people and situations effectively. Whereas, girls are more confined to domestic chores at home and thus have less interaction with people outside the home. Another reason could be more freedom and time given to the boys for games and sports and extra-curricular activities; whereas, girls may tend to have less time for recreational games and sports as they spend more time on doing the household chores and responsibilities.

The study also revealed positive correlation between Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement among the high school students which is consistent with the study of Ganie & Ganai (2021), Dave (2019), Kumar and Mishra (2016); and Shafeeq and Thaqib (2015) but is contradictory to the findings of negative relationship between Emotional Maturity and Academic Performance (Prathibha & Ashok, 2017; Saraswat & Singh, 2015). This implied that one's emotion-positive or negative- can directly or indirectly impact one's performance in one's academic and life as well.

IX. CONCLUSION

The present study focused on studying the Emotional Maturity and Academic Achievement of the high school adolescent students. Results indicated above average Emotional Maturity among the high school students. Though no significant differences were found between the Emotional Maturity of high school students with respect to locality and management yet significant difference was found on the basis of gender. Emotional Maturity was found to positively affect academic achievement of the adolescents.

Adolescents are at a developmental stage where they need care, attention and guidance from parents, teachers and community. The study therefore suggests parents, teachers, schools and community to,

- Provide more social exposure to the students and girls in particular.
- Encourage girls to participate in games and sports.
- Parents and teachers should not be autocratic in dealing with adolescents but provide a reasonable freedom for proper development.
- Encourage students to share their feelings and manage their emotions appropriately.
- Provide more opportunities for their active participation in co-curricular and extra-curricular activities.
- Organise activities that encourage problem solving, decision making, managing emotions and stress management in the students.
- Organise seminars and workshops on resilience building and life skill enhancement among the adolescents.

- Schools should organise parent-teacher meetings and seminars for the parents and teachers for the proper upbringing of the adolescents.
- Assign responsibilities to adolescents in the school and at home to enable them to tackle situations in real life.
- School curriculum should cater to the needs of the students and the community.

This will enable adolescents to develop appropriate social and emotional skills to tackle the challenges of life, enhance their self-worth and relationship with others, and build their capacities to make effective adjustment in the society. Further studies can be conducted on Emotional Maturity with respect to the variables of socio-economic status, birth order, number of siblings, physical health conditions and association with different social groups.

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